

Development of a Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) Algorithm for Suturing Task Automation

1st Antonella Imperato, 2nd Marco Caianiello, 3th Fanny Ficuciello
Universita degli Studi di Napoli, Federico II
 Naples, Italy
 {antonella.imperato}@unina.it

Abstract—Robot-Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (RAMIS) has brought in the last decades major improvements in terms of quality of operations, execution times, patient safety, and post-op rehabilitation. Suturing, however, remains one of the most complex and time-consuming tasks. In this work, we propose a method that uses a Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm, the Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) [1], to generate optimal trajectories for the needle to follow, with the aim to automate, through the use of the da Vinci® surgical system, the execution of needle insertion into the tissue. This method, along with the standard Replay Buffer, involves the use of the Demonstration Buffer, consisting of optimal sequences of states and actions for the agent to achieve, in order to successfully complete the task. In addition, we trained the agent to accomplish more than one goal, through a multiple-goal sparse reward.

Index Terms—Robotic Surgery, Deep Reinforcement Learning, Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient

I. INTRODUCTION

Robot-Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (RAMIS) refers to all surgical procedures performed with the assistance of robotic systems. It was developed with the aim of trying to overcome the limitations introduced by minimally invasive surgery, through teleoperation.

In the last decade, research on surgical robots has focused more on the possibility of equipping these systems with some level of autonomy, to relieve surgeon stress and fatigue. Suture is one of the most complex and time-consuming procedures when it comes to surgical robots. It can be divided into five principal tasks: 1) desired needle position referred to the entry point; 2) needle insertion into the tissue; 3) needle coming out at a desired exit point; 4) re-grasping the needle and thread tensioning; 5) preparing the needle for the next suture point. Our work will focus on points 2) and 3), which refers to needle tissue-crossing.

In this study, a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithm, known as Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG), is proposed to autonomously generate an optimal trajectory for the needle insertion; in addition, we shape a sparse reward with multiple goals. However, since setting more than one goal could lead to the manipulator getting stuck in local optima, we add demonstrations data along with standard Replay Buffer and we tested our work with the da Vinci simulator.

Fig. 1. (a) Experimental setup for CoppeliaSim. (b) Wound Plane and Needle Plane representation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. The State Variables

Following the Markov Decision Process, our agent was the Patient Side Manipulator (PSM) of the da Vinci surgical system, with a curved needle rigidly fixed to its end-effector; the environment was the surgical table with a phantom on it simulating an open wound (Fig. 1a). Starting from the PSM gripper, we traced back to the needle tip through a constant transformation, so that the new end-effector could be considered the needle tip. Starting from the six variables that identify the pose of an object inside the 3D space, we were able to reduce the DDPG state space to only two variables: one for the position and one for the orientation. In fact, to minimize tissue damage, a needle tip trajectory must pass through the entrance and exit points, previously defined on the opposite edges of the wound; in addition, it must remark the needle geometry and be confined in a plane called Needle Plane, which is orthogonal to the one containing the wound, called Wound Plane (Fig. 1b). For this reason, using a semi-circular needle, the path could be approximated as a semi-circular one, with a diameter equal to the needle diameter (d_n); and, once the normal to the needle plane was fixed (z), the remaining two position variables x and y were reduced to one, following the equation of the circle $y = \pm\sqrt{d_n^2 - x^2}$. For the orientation variable, it was set as the angular position θ , that describes the angular shift of the needle around its z -axis. The state space \mathcal{S} was set as:

$$\mathcal{S} = [x \quad \theta] \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Agent's learning curves during training as rate ϵ_d varies. (a) $\epsilon_d = 0$; (b) $\epsilon_d = 0.3$; (c) $\epsilon_d = 0.7$

Along with the standard Experience Replay buffer \mathcal{E} , we used the Demonstration Buffer \mathcal{D} , a sequence of transitions in the same format as \mathcal{E} , whose data were collected mainly from simulation; that represent the sequences of states, next states, actions and rewards necessary to get the desired behavior from the agent. To balance exploration and exploitation, during the training we sampled transitions with a certain probability ϵ_e for \mathcal{E} , and ϵ_d for \mathcal{D} , such that $\epsilon_e + \epsilon_d = 1$.

B. The Reward Function

In this work, we considered a sparse reward function that rewarded the agent for achieving two main goals. For the first one, the needle insertion is successful if the needle reaches a certain depth inside the tissue. Since for every x , through the equation of the circle, we were able to measure y , the maximum depth reached inside the tissue coincided with the point at minimum y , obtained when a change in the slope of the curve occurred:

$$y_{slope,t} \neq y_{slope,t-1} \quad \wedge \quad K\%r_n \leq |y_t| \leq r_n \quad (2)$$

where r_n is the maximum possible depth, equal to needle radius, $K\%$ is the rate that we set equal to 0.9. For the second

and last goal, it was set as the needle tip reaching a desired final pose at the exit point; this goal was formulated as follows:

$$|e_p| \leq e_{p,max} \quad \wedge \quad |e_o| \leq e_{o,max} \quad (3)$$

where e_p and e_o are, respectively, the position and the orientation errors. Setting more than one goal could led the manipulator to oscillate around intermediate states, in an attempt to earn a higher score. Therefore, our reward function R was designed as follows:

$$R = \sum_{t=1}^T (P_{next,t} - P_{back,t} - P_{bound,t}) \quad (4)$$

where P_{next} is 1 every time the agent reaches one of the two goals for the first time, 0 otherwise; P_{back} is 1 every time the agent reaches one of the two goals more than once, otherwise it is 0; P_{bound} is 1 if the manipulator goes outside joints or space limits, 0 otherwise. Therefore, if at the end of the episode $R = 0$, it means that the manipulator has just explored the environment randomly without getting any reward.

III. RESULTS

Tests were conducted inside the da Vinci simulation, provided by Fontanelli et al. [2] for CoppeliaSim. Training consisted of 250 episodes, 200 epochs each; results presented were achieved by comparing standard DDPG with DDPG that made use of the buffer \mathcal{D} , with two different rates ϵ_d : first 0.3 and then 0.7. Oscillatory behaviour is typical in scenarios where more than one goal is set. In Fig.2 it can be observed that the use of \mathcal{D} reduces fluctuations and accelerates the learning process, promoting stability: comparing the first case, where only \mathcal{E} is used ($\epsilon_d = 0, \epsilon_e = 1$), with the last case where the percentage of \mathcal{D} is higher than \mathcal{E} ($\epsilon_d = 0.7, \epsilon_e = 0.3$), stability could be reached almost immediately, approximately 50 epochs earlier than standard DDPG.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we tested the DDPG algorithm to automate needle insertion with da Vinci surgical robot. We designed a sparse reward that discouraged hitting the same target more than once, in order to accomplish multiple goals. In addition to \mathcal{E} we used \mathcal{D} , and saw that demonstrations promote stability and speed up training. In the future, one may think to automate the whole suturing process and take demonstrations from the surgeon itself, to mimic its suturing style as well. This study could be improved in the future by accounting for interaction forces in order to predict tissue stiffness and enhance suturing efficacy even in the presence of tissue deformations [3].

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